

E-SKILLS MATCH HANDBOOK

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List of abbreviations

<Abbreviation>	<Explanation>
Adfor	Adfor S.p.A
DoW	Description of Work
EASQ	European Area of Skills and Qualifications
EC DG CONNECT	European Commission Communications Networks, Content and Technology Directorate General
EC	European Commission
e-CF	European e-Competence Framework
EQF	European Qualifications Framework
EU	European Union
FPM	Fondazione Politecnico di Milano
Gov2u	Government To You
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
M1	Month 1
MOOCS	Massive Open Online Courses
OER	Open Education Resources
SU	Stockholm University
UAH	Universidad de Alcalá
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction to the user guide for the e-Skills Match Platform

Welcome to the e-Skills Match platform!

This platform is co-funded by European Commission Directorate General for Communications Networks, Content & Technology (DG CONNECT), Unit for Inclusion, Skills and Youth. It is a web-based platform for knowledge networking related to e-Skills and digital competences demand and supply in different sectors of the ICT sector. By the offered solution of the e-Skills Match platform the users will be able to meet the contemporary ICT job market's needs, (*ICT professionals*), find the best candidates for ICT job position (*employers/ICT recruiters*) and promote their online courses (training institutions).

In a glance, the registered users will be able to access the following services:

- Detect e-Skills and digital competences required for different ICT occupations;
- Create their individual e-Portfolio – it is an electronic collection of evidence reflecting their professional and academic background that can serve as an electronic resume;
- Knowledge elicitation and representation - Mapping of current e-Skills and levels of digital competences visualized on a Career Concept Map.
- Perform e-Skills audits in order to identify the individual's e-Skills gaps.

This Handbook (user guide) is designed to explain the functioning of each service (tool) that is included in the project's platform. It provides to the reader a step-by-step explanation accompanied with screenshots from the e-Skills Match platform. By using this practice we eliminate any kind of barriers that would demotivate the individuals of testing, using and exploring its full capabilities.

We hope that this document will be helpful and will assist you in comprehending all functions of our platform. However, if this guide cannot answer your query you can contact the e-Skills Match [Helpdesk](#).

Thank you!

The e-Skills Match Consortium

2 Categories of Users

The users of e-Skills Match platform are consisted of the following two main categories.

- **Registered members:** individuals (users) who have been given their own username and password. The users are able to create three types of profile:
 - **Basic profile:** provide information about his/her current e-skills and digital competences, identify the e-skills and digital competences associated with that occupation that he/she need to acquire and find the possible learning paths that will help him/her to acquire them.
 - **Training Institution Profile:** add/edit information of the training institution profile, add the online courses that it offers to the e-Skills Match platform, provide information concerning the online courses such as course type, its cost in euro currency, certificate type
 - **Employer Profile:** add/edit information of the employer's profile, search for potential employees, contact with job-seeker via the e-Skills Match platform
- **Administrators:** users who have access to the entire platform, being able to manage the registered members, the different available tools, the parameters of the platform. They are representatives of the institution that manages this platform.

3 User registration

This section provides to the reader a step-by-step explanation on how users can register at the e-Skills Match platform. Registration can be made either by creating a personal account or by using social network authentication. The following subsections 5.1 and 5.2 present in detail the registration process.

3.1 Register yourself to the platform by not using social network authentication

Step 1: Click "Log in" at the top right of the [platform's home page](#). You will be redirected to the "Sign In" form. In this form click on the link "create an account".

Figure 1 : Create account

Step 2: Enter your **full name** (*first and last name*), your **email address** and your **password** into the relevant fields. After entering the password that you wish to apply, please **verify** it (enter the same password) in the field "Verify password".

Figure 2 : Registration form

Step 3: After filling in all the fields of the form you press the "Register" button. You will receive an email to your inbox for validating your account.

Figure 3 : Validation email

By receiving the validation email you need to click to the respective link for validating your email account.

Step 4: By clicking on the link for validating your email you will be redirected to your profile. Before start using your profile you need to read the privacy policy, scroll down to the bottom and press "**I agree**" in order to continue.

By completing all the above steps you register yourself successfully at the e-Skills Match platform.

3.2 Register yourself to the platform by using social network authentication

Step 1: Click "Log in" at the top right of the [platform's home page](#). You will be redirected to the "Sign In" form. Click on the button "Sign in with Facebook".

Figure 4 : Registration via Facebook

Step 2: Check the box "Agree" with the Privacy Policy. If this is your first time accessing this platform using Facebook authentication, you will be informed about what personal data e-Skills Match platform will need to access for your profile.

Step 3: In order to finish your registration, you must agree to provide the listed personal data from Facebook.

4 Account settings types

The platform has three types of account settings:

- Basic Profile:** It is addressed to users who want to measure up their e-skills and improve their competences by attending online courses. Moreover this category includes the job seekers.
- Training Institution Profile:** It is addressed to users who are representatives of training institutions and want to provide to the e-Skills Match platform training material (*online courses*).
- Employer Profile:** It is addressed to users who are interested to find employees for their company (*or the company that they represent i.e. Human Resources department*)

Account settings can be found on the profile control panel (*figure 6*), which is located at the top right of the platform and activation is realized by clicking on the avatar image (*figure 5*).

Figure 5 : Avatar image

Figure 6 : Profile control panel

5 Manage profiles

The current section presents to the reader how each profile type of the platform can be managed. Concerning the “*Training Institution profile*” and the “*Employer profile*”, explanation is also provided on how users can register and create these profile accounts.

5.1 Manage your Basic profile (Personal Account)

Step 1: After creating your Basic Profile, you can manage your personal account by clicking to the button “Manage Account” (figure 7).

Figure 7 : Manage account button

Step 2: By clicking on the “Manage Account” button, you will be redirected in the platform to the form that contains your personal details.

Figure 8 : Manage your Personal Account

Step 3: Fill in/correct the fields you wish in this form (figure 8)

Step 4: Upload a personal photo (or logo) to your basic profile by clicking on the profile image (figure 9) and selecting from your computer the image that you wish. After completing this process your new profile image will have been uploaded.

Figure 9 : Profile image location (Basic profile)

Step 5: Click on the “Save changes” button (figure 11) in order to complete this process.

Figure 10 : “Save changes” button location within the form

Figure 11 : “Save changes” button

Notation: You can follow all the aforementioned steps as many times as you wish in order to edit your profile.

5.2 Register yourself as a Training institution & Manage the profile

Step 1: Open the account settings window by clicking on the avatar image (see figure 5).

Step 2: After opening the accounts setting window, click on the option “Show courses” (figure 12)

Figure 12 : Show courses

Step 3: After opening the “Show courses” window, click on the option “Profile” (figure 13) in order to register as Training institution.

Figure 13 : Location of “Profile” option (Training institution profile)

Step 4: Fill in the fields with the relevant information of the training institution that you represent.

Figure 14 : Manage Institution Account

Step 5: Upload a logo to your training institution profile by clicking on the profile image (*figure 15*) and selecting from your computer the image that you wish. After completing this process your new profile image will be uploaded.

Figure 15 : Profile image location (Training institution profile)

Step 6: Click on the “Save changes” button (*figure 16*) in order to complete this process.

The screenshot shows the 'Manage Institute Account' page in the Skills Match system. The page has a navigation bar with 'Dashboard', 'Self Assessment', 'Training', and 'ePortfolio' options. Below the navigation bar, there are links for 'Profile', 'Show courses', and 'Add a new course'. The main content area is titled 'Manage Institute Account' and contains several input fields: 'Institute name', 'Institute email', 'Institute city', 'Company country' (set to 'Greece'), 'Institute street address', and 'Institute web address'. There is also a 'Summary' section with a text area. A 'Save changes' button is highlighted with a red circle. Below the form, there are 'Profile options' including 'Download your personal data', 'Delete your profile picture', and 'Delete everything associated with this user'.

Figure 16 : “Save changes” button (Training institution profile)

Notation: You can follow all the aforementioned steps as many times as you wish in order to edit your profile.

5.3 Register yourself as an Employer & Manage the profile

Step 1: Open the account settings window by clicking on the avatar image (see figure 5).

Step 2: After opening the accounts setting window, click on the option “Search employees” (figure 17)

Figure 17 : Search employees

Step 3: After opening the “Search employees” window, click on the option “Profile” (figure 18) in order to register as an Employer.

Figure 18 : Location of “Profile” option (Employer profile)

Step 4: Fill in the fields with the relevant information concerning the Employer account (i.e. the company that you represent).

Figure 19 : Manage Employer Account

Step 5: Upload a logo to your Employer profile by clicking on the profile image (*figure 20*) and selecting from your computer the image that you wish. After completing this process your new profile image will be uploaded.

Figure 20 : Profile image location (Employer profile)

Step 6: Click on the “Save changes” button (*figure 21*) in order to complete this process.

Figure 21 : “Save changes” button (Employer profile)

Notation: You can follow all the aforementioned steps as many times as you wish in order to edit your profile.

5.4 Profile options

All profile types of the e-Skills Match platform have the following options at the bottom of the profile account. The options that the user has in his/her account are:

- Download your personal data;
- Delete your profile picture;
- Delete everything associated with this user.

The following picture depicts the location of these options (*figure 22*). The provided example is a screenshot of the ‘Basic Profile’.

Figure 22 : Profile options location (example)

5.4.1 Download your personal data

Step 1: Click on the option “Download your personal data”

Figure 23 : Location of the option “Download your personal data”

Step 2: The download process starts (figure 24). After the download process is completed, the data is available at your computer.

Figure 24 : Download process

5.4.2 Delete your profile picture

The deletion of the profile picture of your account can be easily made by clicking on the option “Delete your profile picture”. For uploading a new profile picture you can follow the steps that were mentioned in the previous sections on how to manage your profiles (see sections 7.1, 7.2 & 7.3).

Profile options

Figure 25 : “Delete your profile picture” option

5.4.3 Delete everything associated with this user

Step 1: If you wish to remove all data associated with your account you can click on the option “Delete everything associated with this user” (figure 26)

Profile options

Figure 26 : “Delete everything associated with this user” option

Step 2: After clicking the option “Delete everything associated with this user” a pop-up window opens (figure 27) where you need to confirm your choice by clicking “Confirm”.

Figure 27 : Confirm button

6 Login/Logout

The Login/Logout section showcases at first how the registered users can login (see 8.1 Login) to the platform using the options that the e-Skills Match system provides. Following, the Logout process is explained (see section 8.2 Logout).

6.1 Login

6.1.1 Login directly via the Platform

If you visit directly the platform using its URL (<https://platform.eskillsmatch.eu/>), you click "Log in" at the top right of the platform's home page (see figure 28).

Figure 28 : "Log In" location at the project's platform

6.1.2 Login directly via the project's informational website

If you wish to Login to the platform via the project's informational website you click on the "Join" option at the menu from the menu bar (figure 29)

Figure 29 : "Join" location at project's informational website

6.1.3 Sign In

After selecting either the informational website (section 8.1.1) or directly the platform (section 8.1.2) to login you will be redirected to the "Sign In" form (figure 30).

LET'S BEGIN YOUR E-COMPETENCE SELF-ASSESSMENT

A screenshot of the 'Sign In' form. At the top is a blue button with a white Facebook 'f' icon and the text 'Sign in with Facebook'. Below this is a horizontal line with 'OR' in the center. Underneath are two input fields: 'Login' and 'or create an account'. Below these are two more input fields: 'Email address' (with an envelope icon) and 'Password' (with a lock icon). At the bottom left are two checkboxes: 'Stay signed in' and 'Forgot your password?'. At the bottom center is a teal button with the text 'Log In'.

Figure 30 : "Sign In" form

The system provides to the users two options for the sign in process. You can either Sign In with Facebook (see 8.1.3.1 Sign In with Facebook) or by completing the Log In form (see 8.1.3.2 Sign in with Username & password)

6.1.3.1 Sign In with Facebook

LET'S BEGIN YOUR E-COMPETENCE SELF-ASSESSMENT

A screenshot of the 'Sign In' form, identical to Figure 30. The blue button for 'Sign in with Facebook' is circled in red to highlight it.

Figure 31 : Sign In with Facebook

6.1.3.2 Sign In with Username & password

If you have registered yourself in the platform by not using social network authentication (see 5.1 section) follow the steps below.

LET'S BEGIN YOUR E-COMPETENCE SELF-ASSESSMENT

A screenshot of the Skills Match login interface. At the top, there is a blue button with a Facebook 'f' icon and the text 'Sign in with Facebook'. Below this is a horizontal line with 'OR' in the center. Underneath, the text 'Login' is on the left and 'or create an account' is on the right. There are two input fields: 'Email address' with an envelope icon and 'Password' with a lock icon. Below these fields is a checkbox labeled 'Stay signed in' and a link 'Forgot your password?'. At the bottom, there is a teal button labeled 'Log in'. A red circle is drawn around the 'Email address' and 'Password' fields.

Figure 32 : Sign In with Username & password

Step 1: Fill in your Email address and your password in the respective fields.

Step 2: After entering your Email address and your password you can click on the check box “Stay signed in” in case you wish the system to save your credentials. By clicking on the check box you will avoid entering them again when you will return in the platform.

LET'S BEGIN YOUR E-COMPETENCE SELF-ASSESSMENT

The screenshot shows the login interface of the e-Skills Match platform. At the top, there is a blue button with the Facebook logo and the text "Sign in with Facebook". Below this, a horizontal line with "OR" in the center separates it from the standard login form. The form includes a "Login" label and a link "or create an account". There are two input fields: "Email address" and "Password". Below the password field, there is a checkbox labeled "Stay signed in" which is currently checked and highlighted with a red circle. To the right of the checkbox is a link "Forgot your password?". At the bottom of the form is a teal "Log in" button.

Figure 33 : Stay signed In checkbox

If you wish to fill in again your credentials the next time that you will visit the e-Skills Match platform you can click again on the check box and this option will be de-activated. The check box will change color filling from orange to white as it is depicted on figure 34.

LET'S BEGIN YOUR E-COMPETENCE SELF-ASSESSMENT

This screenshot is identical to Figure 33, showing the same login interface. However, the "Stay signed in" checkbox is now unchecked, and its fill color is white. A red arrow points to the checkbox from the left side of the page.

Figure 34 : De-activate the "Stay signed In" option

Step 3: After completing the above steps you click on the Log In button and you enter the e-Skills Match platform.

LET'S BEGIN YOUR E-COMPETENCE SELF-ASSESSMENT

Figure 35 : Log In button

6.1.3.2.1 Forgot your password?

In case you have forgotten your password you click on the option “Forgot your password?” (figure 36).

LET'S BEGIN YOUR E-COMPETENCE SELF-ASSESSMENT

Figure 36 : Forgot your password?

Step 1: After clicking on the option “**Forgot your password?**” a short pop up window will appear where you will need to enter your email. After entering your email

Figure 37 : Enter your email to recover your password

Step 2: After entering your email, you click on the button “Recover password” (figure 38) and you will receive at your email account a message as shown on figure 39.

Figure 38 : “Recover password” button

Figure 39 : “Recover password” button

Step 3: In order to complete this process you click on the link “Click here to change your password” and you will be redirect to the platform (*figure 40*) where you will need to fill in the form with your new password and verify it.

Figure 40 : Reset your password

Step 4: Click on the button “Reset” and your new password will be activated.

6.2 Logout

Step 1: In order to Logout from the e-Skills Match platform at first you click on the avatar image (*figure 41*).

Figure 41 : Avatar image (Logout)

Step 2: A pop up window that concerns your account will open where you can find the “Sign out” option as shown on figure 42.

Figure 42 : Location of “Sign out” option

Step 3: Click on the “Sign out” option.

7 Main Menu

The Main Menu of the e-Skills Match platform is consisted by the following options (main functions):

- **Dashboard**
- **Self-assessment**
- **Training**
- **e-Portfolio**

Figure 43 : Main Menu

7.1 Dashboard

The dashboard is a quick access point to the user's actions in the prototype as well as a reference to important information related and according to their Self-Assessment results.

Figure 44 : Dashboard

7.2 Self-assessment

7.2.1 Complete your own self-assessment

In the main menu at the top of the page click "Self-Assessment" and then "Competences Self-Assessment". Fill in your estimated proficiency level for each respective competence. Consult the information text by clicking on a listed competence. The self-assessment consists of 5 pages. Clicking "Save and continue" will take you to the next page of the assessment. Clicking "Go to results" will complete the assessment and disregard and further assessment pages. The

following section **9.2.2 Self-assessment Pages** provides a detail description on how the user can fill in his/her self-assessment.

7.2.2 Self-assessment Pages

The Self-Assessment is consisted of five pages:

- Plan;
- Build;
- Run;
- Enable;
- Manage.

The figure below depicts the icons that represent each of the aforementioned pages.

Figure 45 : Self-assessment pages

The structure of each page is the same as it is consisted by two main columns, the competences on the left and the proficiency level on the right. The proficiency levels are measured in scale from 1 to 5. However, not all competences have all the proficiency levels.

Additionally, on the left there is box that provides to the user an explanatory text which briefly describes each competence and what each competence level means.

Lastly, at the bottom of each page there is the “save and continue” button and the “go to results” button.

P L A N	Competences	Proficiency levels					IS and Business Strategy Alignment Anticipates long term business requirements, influences improvement of organisational process efficiency and effectiveness. Determines the IS model and the enterprise architecture in line with the organisation's policy and ensures a secure environment. Makes strategic IS policy decisions for the enterprise, including sourcing strategies.												
	IS and Business Strategy Alignment	<input type="checkbox"/> n/a	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5											
	Service Level Management	<input type="checkbox"/> n/a	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5											
	Business Plan Development	<input type="checkbox"/> n/a	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5											
	Product/Service Planning	<input type="checkbox"/> n/a	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5											
	Architecture Design	<input type="checkbox"/> n/a	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5											
	Application Design	<input type="checkbox"/> n/a	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5											
	Technology Trend Monitoring	<input type="checkbox"/> n/a	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5											
	Sustainable Development	<input type="checkbox"/> n/a	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5											
	Innovating	<input type="checkbox"/> n/a	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4		<input type="checkbox"/> 5											
<input type="button" value="save and continue"/> <input type="button" value="go to results"/>							<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Levels</th> <th>Skills</th> <th>Knowledges</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>4</td> <td colspan="2">Provides leadership for the construction and implementation of long term innovative IS solutions.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td colspan="2">Provides IS strategic leadership to reach consensus and commitment from the management team of the enterprise.</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3" style="text-align: center;"> need more help?												
Levels	Skills	Knowledges																	
4	Provides leadership for the construction and implementation of long term innovative IS solutions.																		
5	Provides IS strategic leadership to reach consensus and commitment from the management team of the enterprise.																		
need more help?																			

Figure 46 : Page Structure

Each page (i.e. plan, build, run, enable & manage) can be filled in by the user in any order he/she wishes and doesn't have to select all the competences. The user can fill in only the ones that he/she thinks that apply to him/her. However, the user's results will be more accurate if he/she gives more information. For reader's ease an example is provided on the following figures

Competences	Proficiency levels					
IS and Business Strategy Alignment	n/a	1	2	3	4	5
Service Level Management	n/a	1	2	3	4	5
Business Plan Development	n/a	1	2	3	4	5
Product/Service Planning	n/a	1	2	3	4	5
Architecture Design	n/a	1	2	3	4	5
Application Design	n/a	1	2	3	4	5
Technology Trend Monitoring	n/a	1	2	3	4	5
Sustainable Development	n/a	1	2	3	4	5
Innovating	n/a	1	2	3	4	5

save and continue

go to results

Figure 47 : Competences and proficiency levels

Select from the list of Proficiency level the option that best represents the level that you have on each competence.

You can click on the title of the competence, e.g. “IS and Business Strategy Alignment” and find the explanation of it. Not all competences can be rated from 1 to 5 proficiency level. Lastly there is the option “n/a” (not available) for competences that you don’t have at all.

IS and Business Strategy Alignment

n/a 1 2 3 4 5

Figure 48 : Example of a competence and its proficiency level

 IS and Business Strategy Alignment

Anticipates long term business requirements, influences improvement of organisational process efficiency and effectiveness. Determines the IS model and the enterprise architecture in line with the organisation's policy and ensures a secure environment. Makes strategic IS policy decisions for the enterprise, including sourcing strategies.

Levels	Skills	Knowledges
4		Provides leadership for the construction and implementation of long term innovative IS solutions.
5		Provides IS strategic leadership to reach consensus and commitment from the management team of the enterprise.

 need more help?

Figure 49 : Explanation & help

In this section is all the information you'll need to help you understand each competence, their proficiency levels, the skills and the knowledge. If you need more help or watch this platform tour again just click the 'need more help?' button at the bottom of this section.

After filling in all the competences that you think that apply to you, you can click the button "Save and continue" and it will take you to the next page of the assessment.

save and continue

Figure 50 : Save and continue button

Notation: Remember that you can navigate to any page any time you wish and you can always return to any of the page's section and make any further changes.

Figure 51 : Go to results button

By clicking the "Go to results" button you will finish the self-assessment. Your results will be calculated and you will move to the next section to view your matching job profiles and the breakdown of all your results.

Below a step by step example accompanied with figures is provided.

Example:

Step 1: Your top 4 job profile will appear here, click on the title to view the job profiles breakdown. (figure 52)

Figure 52 : Your top 4 job profiles matches

The check icon means that you fulfill the criteria to this job profile. The 'X' icon means that you lack some competences.

Figure 53 : "Check icons" & "X icons"

Notation: By clicking the “ePortfolio button” you will go to the ePortfolio section to add your evidences for this job profile (see section 9.3). By clicking the ‘Training’ you will find training courses that are available for this job profile (see section 9.2).

7.2.3 Find out how you measure up for specific job profiles

After completing your Self-Assessment, click on the main menu "Self-Assessment" and "eCompetence Map". Here you can view how well you match up to various available job profiles. Click on any job profile to read in detail the criteria that is required.

Figure 54 : Summary of the selected job profile

7.2.4 View your “score” for a desired job profile and find out which competences you are lacking in

Step 1: Click the main menu "Self-Assessment" and "eCompetence Map".

Figure 55 : Self-assessment location on the main menu

In this step you can see how well your skills and competences measure up for various job profiles.

Step 2: Click on any job profile to read in detail what criteria is required. Each competency listed shows both the required level of proficiency and your current level of proficiency.

Figure 56 : Criteria of a job profile

Step 3: To increase your proficiency in a particular competence click the "Training"-button. This takes you to a page providing suggested courses to improve your level.

Figure 57 : "Training" button

7.2.5 Return to your own self-assessment & adjust your previously entered details

To adjust any previously selected proficiency levels, you can click on the "Go to your self-assessment" and make the respective changes concerning your competences' level. After re-selecting the level that you wish do not forget to click on the "Save and continue" button. For viewing your "new" results you click on the "go to results" button.

1

7.3 Training

7.3.1 Find out how you measure up for specific job profiles

Step 1: To increase your proficiency in a particular competence click the "Training"-button as shown in figure 56.

Step 2: After clicking on the "Training" button the platform takes you to a page that provides suggested courses in order to improve your level.

Figure 58 : Suggested courses

Step 3: Click on the "Enroll now" to proceed in your training.

7.3.2 "Training" option at the Main Menu

By clicking on the Training option at the main menu you will be able to view the top training selections according to your results. All the available courses will help you to improve your skills.

Figure 59 : Top training selections

Additionally, you can use the filters in order to find the course that suits you (figure 61).

Figure 60 : Filters' location

7.4 ePortfolio

The ePortfolio is where users can present their own experiences and evidences as entries in their own personal timeline.

7.4.1 Add some experiences to your own ePortfolio

Step 1: In the main menu at the top of the page click "ePortfolio".

Step 2: At the right side of the profile image, click the "Experience" button.

Figure 61 : "Experience" button

Step 3: Complete the fields and press “Confirm”.

Figure 62 : Add your experience

7.4.2 Add evidence to your own ePortfolio

Step 1: In the main menu at the top of the page click "ePortfolio".

Step 2: At the right side of the profile image (next to the "Experience" button) click on the "Evidence" button (see figure 64).

Figure 63 : “Evidence” button

Step 3: Fill in the respective fields and then upload from your computer the evidence that you wish by clicking on the “Browse” button.

Figure 64 : Add evidence

Step 4: After completing Step 3 click on the “Confirm” button.

7.4.3 Adjust an existing experience in your ePortfolio

Step 1: In the main menu at the top of the page click "ePortfolio".

Step 2: Find an existing Experience in the timeline and click the edit icon.

Figure 65 : Edit icon

Step 3: Adjust the experience and save the changes by clicking on the “Confirm” button.

7.4.4 Delete an existing experience in your ePortfolio

Step 1: In the main menu at the top of the page click "ePortfolio".

Step 2: Find an existing Experience in the timeline and click the trash can icon.

Figure 66 : Trash icon

7.4.5 Customize your choices of privacy by choosing which experiences you would like public and which not

Step 1: In the main menu at the top of the page click "ePortfolio".

Step 2: Find an existing Experience in the timeline and click on the eye icon.

Figure 67 : Eye icon

Here you can choose either to show or hide this experience from the public.

7.4.6 Customize your choices of privacy by choosing which competences you would like public and which not

Step 1: Click "Dashboard" in the main menu.

Step 2: Click the button "View and manage your competences".

Figure 68 : “View and manage your competences” button

Step 3: After clicking on "View and manage your competences" you can choose to show or hide individual competences from the public.

Figure 69 : Hide & Show competences options

Notation: Hiding your competences will make sure employers can't find your profile while filtering said competences.

7.5 Notification area

The platform can be also used as a mean of direct communication among employers and job seekers. The messages that the user will receive from employers will be indicated in this area. A bell icon is used and a number to show how many messages have been received in user's account (figure 71).

Figure 70 : Notification area

Step 1: Click on the icon to view the sender, the subject and the date that the message was sent.

YOUR TOP 4 JOB PROFILES MATCHES

Figure 71 : Quick view of the message

Step 2: Click on the message (or click on “Go to your inbox” button) in order to access your message inbox.

Figure 72 : User’s inbox (example)

On the right side of every message an ‘ice cream’ icon is used to represent whether a message has been read or not. If there is a bite mark on the ‘ice cream’ it means that the user has already opened the message (figure 74), if not it means that it is unread.

Figure 73 : Seen Message

Step 3: The user can reply to the message by selecting it and clicking on the ‘Reply’ link on the top right hand side.

Figure 74 : “Reply” link

Step 4: Write your message in the “Message” area and click the “Send” button.

Figure 75 : Reply Message

8 Search for potential employees for your company

Step 1: Click "Profile" (avatar image) in the top right of the platform (see figure 5).

Step 2: Click on the option "Search employees"

Figure 76 : "Search employees" option

Step 3: After clicking on the option "Search employees" you will be redirected to the "Search" page where you can choose the filters that you wish. The filters will help you to find quickly potential employees who match with the desired criteria that you had set.

Figure 77 : "Search employees" filters

Step 4: After selecting the desired criteria you click on the "Search" button and the platform will display the results.

Figure 78 : Search results

Notation: If you wish to make a new search with different criteria you can click on the “Clear filter” button.

Figure 79 : “Clear filter’ button

9 Contact a job seeker using the means provided by the platform

For contacting to a job seeker via the e-Skills Match platform at first you need to take all steps from 1 to 4 as mentioned in section 10 “Search for potential employees for your company”.

Step 1: After completing the aforementioned steps, you click on the name of a jobseeker that you want to contact as shown in the example that is provided in figure 81.

Figure 80 : Click on the name of a job-seeker

Step 2: Click on the "Personal Info" button.

Figure 81 : “Personal info” button

Step 3: After clicking on the “Personal info” button, a pop up window appears with personal information of the job-seeker and a button of "Contact {username}" as shown on figure 83.

Figure 82 : "Contact {username}" button

Step 4: Click on the "Contact {username}" button, write your message and then click "Send" for sending your message to the job-seeker (figure 84).

Figure 83 : Send message to a job-seeker

10 Privacy Policy

10.1 Find the Privacy policy

Figure 84 : Privacy Policy

Click the link "Privacy Policy" at the bottom right of the page. In **Appendix 1** the reader can find the privacy policy as presented in the platform.

10.2 Download all your personal data that has been stored by this platform

Click "Profile" in the top right. Click your name under the "Profiles" column. At the bottom of the profile page click "Download your personal data". You can find a step by step explanation accompanied with figures at section "7.4.1 Download your personal data" of this document.

11 e-Skills Match Helpdesk

This document aims to assist the users while using the e-Skills Match platform. However, if you have any other queries or you meet any kind of difficulty you can contact with the platform's helpdesk. The e-Skills Match helpdesk support is provided online, on an ongoing basis during working hours (Monday to Friday except public holidays, 09:00 am to 17:30 pm). Priority will be given in answering questions sent during working hours as described above. The user support services are available in English, Greek, Italian, Spanish and Swedish languages

In order to contact with the platform's helpdesk, please follow the steps below.

Step 1: Click "Profile" (avatar image) in the top right of the platform (*see figure 5*).

Step 2: In the popup, click on the option "Contact our Helpdesk", located under the "Support" column.

Figure 85 : Contact our Helpdesk

Step 3: First from the top down menu of "Type of contact" you select a value from the provided options that concerns your query. The options are:

- Self-assessment
- Training
- ePortfolio
- Managing courses
- Employer
- Other

After selecting one value from the aforementioned you write your name, your email and your message at the respective fields (*see figure 87*).

HelpDesk

We are here to assist! If you have any questions regarding the platform don't hesitate to contact our HelpDesk. We will get back to you as soon as possible.

Required*

Type of contact

Name *

e-mail *

Message

Figure 86 : Contact our Helpdesk

Step 4: Enter the captcha password in order to verify that your request is sent by a real user.

HelpDesk

We are here to assist! If you have any questions regarding the platform don't hesitate to contact our HelpDesk. We will get back to you as soon as possible.

Required*

Type of contact

Name *

e-mail *

Message

Figure 87 : Captcha field

Step 5: After entering the captcha code you click the “Submit” button and the process of contacting with the Helpdesk team has been completed.

12 e-Skills Match Newsletter registration

You can sign up for receiving the e-Skills Match newsletter by following the steps below.

Step 1: Scroll down to the bottom of the platform’s page.

Figure 88 : Newsletter registration form

Step 2: Enter your email address in the field "Sign up for our Newsletter"

Step 3: Click on the button "Go" and your registration will be completed.

Figure 89 : "Go" button

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